

INFLUENCE OF MOISTURE GRADIENTS ON THE BENDING PROPERTIES IN SHORT GLASS FIBER REINFORCED POLYAMIDE

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ABSTRACT

Polyamides are known to be able to absorb moisture and as a result their properties and dimensions change significantly. In particular, the mechanical strength is drastically reduced due to the absorption of water, for which reason a mechanical characterization is required both for polyamides and composites with a polyamide matrix depending on the water absorption.

This contribution investigates the alteration of the bending properties of PA6-GF30 by water absorption with different moisture gradients. In addition, the effect of water and mechanical anisotropy due to fiber orientation distribution by injection molding on bending strength is investigated. For this purpose, bending tests are performed at 0° and 90° to the fiber orientation of the specimens in order to determine the bending strength at different moisture gradients.

In the literature the bending properties are mostly determined with homogeneous moisture distributions and different integral moisture contents [1]. This contribution, however, focuses the change of the moisture distribution over an ageing time. During this time, the integral moisture content of the bending beam is kept constant by means of a diffusion barrier. During the ageing time the moisture gradient is degraded by diffusion.

The tests performed show that both the water content and the fiber orientation of the samples have the expected effect on the bending properties of short-glass-fiber-reinforced polyamide 6. When considering the moisture gradient degradation over defined ageing times, an increase in the bending modulus can be observed.

1 INTRODUCTION

Short-glass-fiber reinforced (SGFR) thermoplastics are frequently used in technical applications, especially in the automotive sector, due to their high specific strength and their good processability by injection molding.

The hygroscopic properties of matrix material Polyamide 6 (PA6) enable it to absorb and desorb humidity from the ambient air until the material is in equilibrium with the environment. Components made of PA6 reinforced with glass fibers are usually exposed to significantly different climatic conditions during their technical use, so that the material is rarely in a state of equilibrium with the environment [2]. If the composite is in contact with humidity or exposed in water, the polar liquid water is attracted by the equally polar amide groups present within the molecular chains and settle between the chains under the binding of hydrogen bonds, so that intermolecular interactions are influenced [3]

Due to the occupation of the hydrogen bonds by water molecules, sliding of the molecular chains under external loads is simplified and the cooperative chain segment mobility is increased. This can also be seen in the reduction of the glass transition temperature of the matrix material from approx. 60 °C for dry PA6 to approx. - 20 °C for fully water-saturated PA6. [4]

This material behavior is referred to as the water-induced plasticizing effect, which leads to the drastic reduction in the stiffness of the matrix material and a significant increase in toughness [5]. The

diffusion processes of the water from the outside into the inside of the composite are strongly influenced by various parameters such as temperature, time and morphology of the material [6]. Even a temporary contact of the composite with water inevitably results in the formation of moisture gradients during the ab- or desorption process.

Diffusion processes are used to balance the concentration of water from the boundary layer of the material into the inside of the material until the water concentration in the entire material is equilibrated [6]. Moisture gradients are thus degraded by diffusion processes in the material and, due to the water-induced plasticizing effect, different mechanical properties occur locally in the matrix material [7].

In addition to the influence of moisture on the PA6 matrix material, anisotropy has a major influence on the mechanical properties of injection-molded composite components due to the short glass fiber reinforcement. The strength of an SGFR thermoplastic depends to a large extent on its fiber orientation. In the fiber orientation direction, strength and stiffness are significantly increased compared to perpendicular to the fiber orientation direction, where stiffness decreases and toughness and elongation at break increase. The fiber orientation is not only determined by the part geometry, but also by the positioning, the type of gate and the wall thickness of the part. In addition, the fiber orientation distribution created by various flow processes during the injection molding process must be taken into account. For the geometry of a simple thin plate, which is injected with a film gate, an extensional flow in the core of the plate results in a fiber orientation perpendicular to the melt flow direction, whereas a fiber orientation in melt flow direction called shell layer is formed due to shear flows in the edge areas. In addition, a skin layer with random fiber orientation is formed by freezing due to the rapid cooling of the hot melt on direct contact with the colder mold cavity. Due to the clearly defined fiber orientations within a plate, samples are milled from plates to characterize material properties depending on the fiber orientation. [8,9]

Due to the water-induced plastifying effect of the matrix material and the fiber orientation-dependent material behavior of the composite, there is a complex material behavior for SGFR thermoplastics with PA6 matrix material. It is therefore of particular importance to know how short glass fiber reinforced PA6 components behave when external loads are applied as soon as moisture gradients are present in the material.

The mechanical characterization of the composite is performed by a three-point bending test. The material stress during bending tests is highest at the boundary layer of the bending beam, because here the highest deflection is present in the bending line. The neutral fiber lies inside a bending beam, which, assuming linear-elastic material behavior, is stress- and strain-free. Due to the conditioning method used for the samples in the water bath, the outer boundary layer is completely saturated with water immediately after taking a sample from the bath, and the moisture gradient to the dry core of the sample is maximum - this leads to a significant reduction in the matrix bending stiffness in the boundary area most severely stressed by the bending test.

The moisture gradient decomposes within the specimens by means of diffusion processes within an ageing period. An exchange with the environmental moisture is prevented by a diffusion barrier, so that the integral moisture content is maintained. The bending tests are repeated at defined measuring intervals so that the bending properties can be investigated by reducing the moisture gradient. In order to determine an influence of the fiber orientation of the SGFR thermoplastic, these tests are performed on bending beams milled from plates with known fiber orientation, whereby the orientation of the bending beams is determined at an angle of 0° and 90° to the melt flow direction of an injection-molded plate made of PA6 with 30 weight % of short glass fiber reinforcement (PA6-GF30).

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Material

A short glass fiber reinforced polyamide 6 with 30% glass fibers by weight (Altech PA6 A 2030109 GF30, Albis Plastics GmbH, Germany) is used for the experiments. Plates (90 mm x 90 mm x 2 mm) are injection molded using a film gate. Bending beams (40 mm x 4 mm x 2 mm) are milled out of these, under consideration of the melt flow direction under 0° and under 90° to the fiber orientation direction of the plate. After extraction, the beams are immediately dried for 100 h at 80°C in a vacuum furnace (Heraeus Holding GmbH, Germany) and then annealed for 1 h at 120°C , so that dry samples in the

same ageing state can be assumed and any post-crystallization processes are completed. Directly after removal from the vacuum furnace, the respective dry weight of the samples is determined using a balance (HR-250 A, A&D Company, Japan).

2.2 Sorption Behavior

The determination of the water absorption behavior of the PA6-GF30 used is performed in a water bath at room temperature of 23 °C. For this purpose, ten dry samples with 0° fiber orientation direction and ten dry samples with 90° fiber orientation direction with bending beam geometry are completely immersed in the water bath and stored there. The samples are taken from the water at defined intervals and the surface water wiped off with a lint-free cloth and then weighed. The integral mass fraction of the absorbed water c is determined according to DIN EN ISO 62 using the initial weight m_0 of the sample after vacuum drying and the weight of the sample after water absorption m_1 with the following formula [10]:

$$c = \frac{(m_1 - m_0)}{m_0} \cdot 100 [\%] \quad (1)$$

With this procedure, the sorption behavior is determined up to complete saturation over the entire sample cross-section. This is achieved when a constant weight is reached over several measurements despite water storage. The procedure is performed on ten specimens with fiber orientation direction of 0° and ten specimens with 90° fiber orientation direction.

2.3 Determination of the required conditioning method

The conditioning method for the bending beams is developed on the basis of the sorption curve. To obtain a moisture gradient due to water storage, all samples must be stored in a water bath at 23 °C for a predetermined period of time. Preliminary tests have shown that an integral water content of about 50% of the maximum possible water absorption of the samples is optimal for the tests to be carried out. Higher integral water contents reduce the moisture gradient between the sample boundary layer and the sample core, whereas lower integral water contents increase the effect of re-drying at the sample surface due to interactions with the environment on the measurement results. With the help of the previously determined sorption curve, the storage period of the samples in the water can be determined.

2.4 Ageing with diffusion barrier

The interaction of the material with the environmental air should be prevented so that the adjusted integral water content of the samples can be kept constant and re-drying of the sample edge during the ageing period can be reduced. Preliminary tests have shown that storage of the samples in direct contact with aluminum significantly reduces interaction with the environmental atmosphere. Specimen storage boxes are specially developed for this purpose, in which each individual conditioned bending beam is placed in a separate pocket in an aluminum block. A specimen storage box used for five specimens is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Specimen Storage Box with sealing cord (left) and corresponding cover (right)

The dimensions of the pockets are selected so that the samples have to be tightly fitted. Five pockets are arranged next to each other in each aluminum block, which is tightly sealed with a cover with sealing

cord and four screws.

2.5 Determination of the ageing time and testing intervals

Immediately after conditioning in a water bath, the maximum moisture gradient is between the completely water-saturated sample boundary and the dry sample core. By means of diffusion processes this concentration difference of the water content is degraded until a constant humidity has been reached across the sample cross-section, whereby the same water content is maintained integrally in the sample. In order to determine the influence of a moisture gradient on the bending properties of PA6-GF30 composites, the bending tests are carried out after defined ageing times after sample conditioning. The first bending test is carried out immediately after removal from the water bath. The remaining specimens are stored in the specimen storage boxes until the bending test. The aging times are set to 25 h, 50 h, 100 h, 250 h and 500 h so that the moisture gradient can degrade over the aging time. After 500 h it is assumed on the basis of the sorption curve (see Fig. 4) that there is a homogeneous water distribution over the sample cross-section and that the moisture gradient is completely degraded.

2.6 Bending tests procedure

All 3-point-bending tests are carried out on an *Eplexor 500 N* (Netzsch/Gabo, Germany). For this purpose, specimen supports with a width of 30 mm are used. During the test, the test chamber is kept constant at 23 °C and 50% r.H. using a *Hygromator* (Netzsch/Gabo, Germany), so that constant test conditions are ensured. All specimens are loaded with a constant load speed of 1 mm/min to a deflection of 100% of the specimen height. This results in a bending strain of 2 %. The bending tests are performed according to DIN EN ISO 178 [11] to defined ageing times directly after conditioning (0 h), then after 25 h, 50 h, 100 h, 250 h and 500 h.

For each fiber orientation (0°/90°) and ageing time, five conditioned specimens are tested in the bending test and their results are averaged. In addition, five dry and five water-saturated reference samples are tested for each fiber orientation. Before the measurement, the sample height h and thickness b are determined using a caliper gauge so that the bending stress and bending strain can be calculated by using Formula 2 or Formula 3. In addition, the sample weight of each sample is determined before the measurement so that an integral water content can be calculated for the respective sample after the ageing period and a re-drying over the ageing time can be determined.

$$\sigma_b = \frac{3 \cdot F \cdot L}{2 \cdot b \cdot h^2} [MPa] \quad (2)$$

The bending stress σ_b is given in [MPa] and is calculated with formula (2), where F stands for the applied force in [N], L for the width of the specimen supports in [mm], h for the specimen thickness [mm] and b for the specimen width in [mm].

$$\varepsilon_b = 600 \cdot \frac{h \cdot f}{L^2} [\%] \quad (3)$$

The bending strain ε_b is given in [%] and is calculated with formula (3), where f stands for the deflection in [mm].

In addition, the respective bending modulus is determined from the measured bending stress strain diagrams according to formula 4 and plotted over the ageing time.

$$E_b = \frac{F \cdot L^3}{4 \cdot f \cdot b \cdot h^3} [MPa] \quad (4)$$

The bending modulus E_b is given in [MPa] and is calculated using formula 4 with the measurement parameters listed above. The measurement setup used for the bending tests can be seen in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Bending Test Procedure using *Eplexor 500 N*

4 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Due to its hygroscopic properties, the sorption behavior of PA6-GF30 must be investigated. On the basis of the sorption curves measured, conditioning times in the water bath are estimated for the following investigations. Figure 4 shows the sorption behavior in 0° and 90° fiber orientation.

Figure 4: Sorption curve for 0° (grey curve) and 90° (red curve) fiber orientation direction of the PA6-GF30 used

Figure 4 shows the integral water content of the samples over the ageing time in root hours immersed in the water bath. From the sorption curve shown, it can first be seen that the sorption behavior is almost identical for both fiber orientations. The water content increases linearly over the ageing time in root hours. Within 25 root hours (625 hours) a constant water content of the samples can be observed and complete water saturation is achieved at 6.5 % water content.

For the defined conditioning of the specimens for the bending test, a reproducible integral water

content must be fixed. To ensure that the water distribution immediately after conditioning is as inhomogeneous as possible and that there is a large moisture gradient, 50 % of the maximum saturation is defined as the integral water content, of which 3.25 % is determined by means of the sorption curve for the material and which is achieved after 10 root hours or 100 h aging in the water bath. Table 1 shows the mean integral water content for all sample types.

Sample Type	Water storage Time [h]	Mean Moisture Content [%]	Standard Deviation [%]
0°	100	3.46	0.05
90°	100	3.52	0.35

Table 1: Mean moisture content for the sample types with 0° and 90° fiber orientation direction for a water exposure time of 100 h

The bending measurements at 0 h start directly after the water bath, all further samples are immediately stored in the Specimen Storage Boxes as diffusion barriers and tested after the storage intervals of 25 h, 50 h, 100 h, 250 h and 500 h.

Figure 5: Results of the bending tests performed on specimens with 0° fiber orientation direction after defined ageing times

Figure 5 shows the results of the bending measurements up to 2% bending strain for samples with 0° fiber orientation with the same integral water content but different ageing times. There are hardly any differences in the bending behavior of the specimens over the ageing time, and therefore Figure 6 illustrates the resulting bending modulus of the specimens over the ageing time. In a direct comparison, the flexural modulus for dry (pink) and for completely water-saturated material (light blue) is also shown.

Figure 6: Changes in bending modulus over ageing time and in comparison with dry and water saturated bending modulus for specimens with 0° fiber orientation direction

It can be seen that the bending modulus of about 3900 MPa initially decreases as a result of the aging process, rising to about 4200 MPa over longer aging times of 500 hours. It should be noted that despite a water saturation of only 50% of the maximum saturation, the measured bending modulus falls almost in the range of the bending modulus for fully saturated material of 3300 MPa.

Figure 7 shows the results of the bending measurements up to 2% bending strain for samples with 90° fiber orientation with the same integral water content but measured at different ageing times. In contrast to Figure 5, differences in the bending behavior of the material over the ageing time can be seen, for which reason Figure 8 also considers the measured bending modulus over the ageing time in detail.

Figure 7: Results of the bending tests performed on specimens with 90° fiber orientation direction after defined ageing times

It can be seen that, just as in Figure 6, there is a slight change in the bending modulus from a measured

bending modulus of about 1300 MPa at 0 h to a bending modulus of about 1400 MPa at 100 h, and finally an increase in the bending modulus to about 1500 MPa at 500 h. Again, the measured values of the bending modulus for samples with integral water content of 50 % of maximum saturation are quite close to the measured bending modulus for fully water-saturated samples of 1150 MPa.

Figure 8: Changes in bending modulus over ageing time and in comparison with dry and water saturated bending modulus for specimens with 0° fiber orientation direction over the ageing time

In order to verify the conditioning state, the samples are weighed before the bending measurement, so that a determination of the integral moisture content of the bending beams can be made. This can also be used to quantify re-drying, i.e. a change in the integral water content during the ageing period despite the diffusion barrier in the Specimen Storage Box. Figure 9 shows the re-drying behavior for the samples with 0° fiber orientation as a box plot over the respective ageing time.

Figure 9: Boxplot diagram of the re-drying behavior of the samples with 0° fiber orientation direction over the ageing time

The diagram shows a decrease of the mean integral water content up to the ageing time of 100 h, followed by an increase of the integral water content up to 500 h. This allows conclusions to be made about the expired re-drying during the ageing period, as the mean integral water content at the beginning of the respective ageing periods was in the range of 3.46 ± 0.05 %.

Figure 10: Boxplot diagram of the re-drying behavior of the samples with 90° fiber orientation direction

Figure 10 shows the re-drying behavior for samples with 90° fiber orientation as a box plot over the respective aging time. In a direct comparison with Figure 9, a similar re-drying process can be observed, although here the highest re-drying effect occurs at 50 hours.

5 CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK

The results of the performed series of bending measurements on conditioned samples with integrally equal water content and existing moisture gradients, which are maximum immediately after conditioning (0 h) and minimum degraded after 500 h ageing time, are discussed below. First of all, a clear influence of the fiber orientation on the measured bending properties can be recognized, since the bending strength for 0° to the fiber orientation direction of measured conditioned specimens corresponds to a bending strain of 2% between 110 and 120 MPa, whereas the bending strength for conditioned specimens with 90° fiber orientation at 2% bending strain is only between 40 and 50 MPa.

In addition, a clear influence of the water content on the bending strength can also be observed. The bending moduli measured as a reference for dry specimens are approx. 7000 MPa for 0° fiber orientation and 2750 MPa for 90° fiber orientation, whereas the bending moduli measured for fully water-saturated specimens are approx. 3400 MPa for 0° fiber orientation and 1200 MPa for 90° fiber orientation.

In theory, water diffuses during conditioning in the water bath into the surface layer of the polyamide and from there ever further into the core. Conditioning to 50 % of the maximum possible water saturation results in a clear moisture gradient from a maximum saturation of the boundary layer to the dry core of the material, which is further and further balanced by diffusion over a period of aging with a diffusion barrier, so that after a sufficiently long aging time a constant water content is achieved in the sample.

A three-point bending test load causes the outermost boundary layer of the bending beam to be loaded the most, whereas the neutral fiber inside the bending beam remains unloaded. Due to the conditioning with moisture gradient, the outermost boundary layer is considerably tougher and has a reduced strength compared to the dry interior, for which reason a reduced bending modulus is to be expected. During the degradation of the moisture gradient by diffusion, it can therefore be expected that the bending modulus will increase over the ageing time. The available results of the bending measurement series confirm this

theory, although it should be noted that only a slight increase in the bending modulus over the ageing time is to be measured. In addition, re-drying of the specimens must not be neglected, which also influences the bending strength of the material. However, there is no clear correlation between re-drying and bending modulus. The lowest re-drying and thus the highest water content of the specimens before the bending measurement is determined for both fiber orientations at a storage time of 500 h, which however has the highest bending modulus.

When considering the influence of fiber orientation on the increase in bending strength over the aging time of the conditioned and aged specimens, no clear effect of fiber orientation can be determined. Both the sorption behavior and the increase in the bending modulus of about 200 MPa each over the aging time are almost identical for both fiber orientation directions.

In summary, it should be noted that the presence of a moisture gradient clearly reduces the bending strength of PA6-GF30 compared to a constant moisture content and thus requires an extended characterization of moisture gradients in the material.

Further work will initially focus on the pure matrix material polyamide 6. A thermomechanical characterization of the material in the range of moisture gradients as well as a coupling of the mechanical properties and the water absorption and the coupling of the water absorption under load will be investigated. Furthermore, the influence of water on the morphology of the material is studied. The knowledge gained can then be applied to short glass fiber reinforced polyamide 6.

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